

The impact of cataract surgery on visual acuity and quality of life of patients operated on in University Teaching Hospital of Kigali (CHUK) and Rwanda Charity Eye Hospital (RCEH)

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Introduction

Cataracts, a leading cause of blindness particularly in middle- and low-income countries, are expected to rise with global aging trends. They impair vision, increasing risks of dementia, falls, and accidents, which negatively affect quality of life and can elevate mortality rates. Symptoms include blurred vision, light sensitivity, and night vision difficulties. Cataract surgery is a highly effective treatment with minimal complications. This study aims to assess the impact of cataract surgery on visual acuity and quality of life, focusing on functionality, emotional well-being, social interactions, and overall patient satisfaction.

Materials and Methods

This hospital-based cross-sectional study included patients consecutively from March to July 2024. Data collected encompassed age, gender, comorbid conditions, laterality of cataract, type of surgery, follow-up dates, and visual acuity pre- and post-surgery. A quality of life questionnaire was administered at follow-up. Visual acuity was categorized according to WHO standards, and data were analyzed using SPSS.

Results

Preoperatively, 41.5% of eyes had poor vision (<6/60). Post-surgery, 78.6% achieved good visual acuity (<6/18), 13.5% had borderline visual acuity (<6/18-6/60), and 7.8% retained poor visual acuity. Quality of life data indicated significant preoperative limitations: 22.47% and 38.20% of patients had activity restrictions “all of the time” or “most of the time”, respectively, and 20.22% faced employment and task difficulties due to poor vision. Additionally, patients reported pain, discomfort, and emotional distress. Postoperative results showed marked improvements in quality of life, including reduced daily activity limitations, alleviated pain and discomfort, and enhanced emotional well-being.

Conclusion

The study predominantly involved elderly males with severe preoperative visual impairment. Cataract surgery, mainly PHACO+IOL, significantly improved visual acuity and quality of life. Although age influenced postoperative outcomes, the surgery effectively reduced the negative impacts of poor vision on daily life, work, and emotional health.

Keywords

Cataract surgery, visual acuity, quality of life, Rwanda, University Teaching Hospital of Kigali (CHUK), Rwanda Charity Eye Hospital (RCEH)